

The role of minority political groups in the viral dissemination of disinformation. The case of Spain

Abstract

The impact of social networks such as Twitter on political conversations and the landscape of democracy has been a frequently addressed issue in recent years. This study seeks to understand better the role played by minority political groups in Spain in promoting disinformation on Twitter. The study applies statistical analysis and topic modeling to posts (tweets and retweets) published in Spanish on Twitter (n=19,653 tweets), as well as to content identified as disinformation (n=2,730) by two independent fact-checking projects in Spain from August 2019 to March 2020. The data reveals how the political communication strategy focuses mainly on the confrontation between the majority political groups at national levels and the legitimization of their political projects to their potential voters through specific issues. The data also reveals a co-occurrence between messages published by political actors and content identified as disinformation by the fact-checkers chosen for the analysis. This co-occurrence depends on the tweets' political profile, virality, and sentimental load. The digital presence of Spanish minority political groups on Twitter favors the conditions for the viral dissemination of disinformation, primarily when the content focuses on mobilizing potential voters through emotional messages; and helps fact-checking projects to observe a polarised communicative context and the role assumed by minority political groups in the dissemination of disinformation through Twitter.

Keywords:

Disinformation; politicians; political communication; Twitter; fact-checking.

Introduction

The growth of social networks in recent decades has contributed to the transformation of communication in our societies. The collective perception of the public sphere is shifting, and so is how relationships between individuals are established (Piñeiro-Otero & Martínez-Rolan, 2021). A new generation is emerging in a landscape marked by anonymity, immediacy, and much information. Bauman (2015) calls this phenomenon "liquid modernity," referring to an era marked by the proliferation of content of all sorts. The current communicative framework, which is strongly conditioned by digital

scenarios –as noted by authors such as Lamerichs *et al.* (2018) or Farkas *et al.* (2018)– contributes to a social scenario that tends to increase the violation of tolerance, civility, and respect towards certain groups (Aguilés & Pecourt, 2021; Matamoros-Fernández & Farkas, 2021), and threatens the prevalence of democratic and civil values in our societies (Davidson *et al.*, 2017).

Since 2016, in the aftermath of political events such as Brexit and Donald Trump's electoral victory in the United States, authors such as Søre (2018), Levi (2019), Scheufele and Krause (2019), and Cañabate (2019) have shown how these sorts of events have contributed to a polarisation of our societies promoted by disinformation strategies that condition public opinion (Van der Linden, Maibach, Cook, Leiserowitz and Lewandowsky, 2017).

Despite the difficulties associated with defining what is understood as disinformation, authors such as Wardle and Derakshan (2017) highlight the current existence of a "culture of disinformation" based on "an ecosystem of production, propagation and consumption of false, inaccurate or misleading information that is either for profit or intended to cause public harm" (European Commission, 2018, p. 10). Authors such as Estrada-Cuzcano *et al.* (2020) describe the inherent complexity in defining categories of disinformation.

Hrčková *et al.* (2019) describe the differences between disinformation, fake news and misinformation (table 1).

Table 1.

Differences between **disinformation, fake news and misinformation** (Hrčková, 2019).

Disinformation	Fake news	Misinformation
Focused on the dissemination of deceptive content	Aimed at disseminating information with malicious intent	Aimed at disseminating rumours
Aimed at disseminating information with malicious intent	Aimed at spreading false stories	Aimed at disseminating confusing information
Aimed at disseminating confusing information	Aimed at disseminating confusing information	Aimed at disseminating inaccurate information
Aimed at disseminating inaccurate information	Manipulation-oriented	Aimed at the dissemination of unverified information

Aimed at the dissemination of false information	Focused on the medium in which the information is disseminated	Aimed at the dissemination of false information
	Content that is often widely broadcast	It happens often when sharing information

Other authors such as Olmo (2019) define disinformation as the intentional dissemination of non-rigorous information aimed at conditioning public opinion through the distortion of facts in order to condition the perception of reality. Therefore, disinformation can be varied and does not necessarily have to be entirely false. What is decisive to the definition of disinformation is the intention with which it is generated and disseminated. Thus, while authentic news is published with the legitimate intention of informing the public interest, fake news has no interest in providing factual information, favouring gratification instead and prioritising the emotional component of the content (Correia & Amaral, 2021).

Recent studies on news consumption point to the decline of certain traditional media and the consolidation of new media such as social media (Newman et al., 2021). The growth of social media as a medium for obtaining news in recent years, especially among the youngest and people with lower levels of education, accelerated during the pandemic.

The predominance of social networks reinforces the role of users, not as consumers, but as *prosumers* of information, which is also the case for disinformation. The success of disinformation depends on the collective perception of what is or is not false, and therefore implies the participation of users in its dissemination (Correia, Jerónimo & Gradim, 2019; Correia & Amaral, 2021), in making this type of content viral and generating favourable feelings towards the main postulates they express (Benkler *et al.*, 2020).

There are organisations and social groups (including political groups) interested in manipulating or conditioning public opinion through social networks. These groups contribute to altering the sense of collective credibility online (Bradshaw & Howard, 2017). According to Marwick and Lewis (2017), the last decade has seen the emergence of hyper-partisan networks fuelled by groups with extreme, radicalised ideologies. These networks have managed to disseminate certain messages on social networks, attracting like-minded users and amplifying the impact of their messages (Ardia et al., 2020). Inform of dubious origin that feeds partisan theses is employed by politicians on social

networks who make it part of the conversation to underpin and amplify their positions (Said-Hung et al., 2021; Marwick & Lewis, 2017). The latest research based on systematic observations of concrete scenarios through the cyberpragmatics approach studies the relationship between politicians and their voters (García-Orosa & López-García, 2019). In these studies, Twitter is positioned as one of the main digital scenarios in which ideas are debated and agenda-setting takes place (Frame and Brachotte, 2015) through highly partisan community structures (Guarino et al., 2020). This favours polarisation, the normalisation of a confrontational communicative context and the presence of hate speech at the societal level (Galvañ & Giménez, 2020). In this context, political groups (in our case, in Spain) have a prominent role in making greater use of negative expressions, assertions and insults to attract and generate interactions with their voters, as highlighted by authors such as Galvañ and Giménez (2020), Piazza (2020) and Agarwal *et al.* (2021).

What has been described thus far is perhaps more relevant considering the case of Spain if we take into consideration that its political system favours polarisation (Urman, 2020) due to its "imperfect bipartisanship", as authors such as Sánchez (2017) have called it, referring to the presence of two dominant political groups (in this case, the Partido Socialista Obrero Español and the Partido Popular) that have not been able to control their ideological spaces as a consequence of the presence of other political groups in different territorial areas of Spain (e.g. nationalist parties and/or pro-independence parties). This political scenario has shifted since 2015 to what authors such as Fernández (2016) have called "fragmented multipartyism", defined by the integration of new groups (e.g. Unidas Podemos, Vox, among others) into the Spanish political system (Penadés and Pavía, 2016; Ibañez, 2018). This contributes to a greater complexity when it comes to attracting the necessary voters to be able to have representation within public institutions in Spain. This complexity interacts with current digital stages such as Twitter or Facebook and a polarised, crisis-focused narrative –especially in conservative and/or radical political groups– towards certain issues that attract said voters (Ferreira, 2019; Lupato *et al.*, 2020; Arroyo, 2020; Alonso-Muñoz and Casero-Ripollés, 2021).

Methodology

The aim of this article is to estimate the co-occurrence between Twitter posts by Spanish minority political groups and content identified as misinformation by the main fact-

checking projects in Spain. In order to achieve this objective, this study has the following specific objectives:

- SO1: Estimate the intensity of the words associated with the tweets posted by users of the parties, leaders and spokespersons of the selected political groups.
- SO2: Identify the topics addressed in the tweets of each user associated with the selected political groups, as well as the content identified in Maldita.es and Newtral.es, during the time period in question.
- SO3: Establish the dominant approaches in the political communication strategy applied by the analysed users.
- SO4: Determine the level of co-occurrence between the messages published by the users analysed and the content identified as misinformation on Maldita.es and Newtral.es during the period in question.
- SO5: Estimate the association between the level of co-occurrence observed and the virality and type of tweets published by the users associated with the selected political groups.

The study attempts to answer the following hypotheses:

- H1: Digital communication strategies based on confrontation and polarisation give the selected political groups a prominent role in the dissemination of disinformation at the level of Spanish public opinion.
- H2: The level of co-occurrence between published messages and content identified as disinformation will depend on the political profile of the political groups analysed.

A minority political group (Table 1) is defined as one that meets the following three criteria taken into account for the development of this work:

- It must have an autonomic, as opposed to national, scope of political action. That is, they must operate at the level of autonomous communities in Spain, the first-level political and administrative division in the country.

- It must have had a voting share of 10% or less of the electorate during the general elections for the Presidency of the Government of Spain undertaken in April and November 2019.
- That the votes obtained must have given it political representation in the Spanish Congress of Deputies, the highest stage of political representation in the country.

For this study, we considered all the tweets published by political groups on Twitter in Spanish. A total of 19,653 posts published between 1 September 2019 and 29 February 2020 were gathered. Posts in other languages (English, Galician, Catalan or Basque) were excluded, given that the work focuses on the official language of the entire Spanish territory, used within the national political debate, beyond the scope of political action (autonomic and national) and the political profile of each group (table 1), in accordance with the findings of authors such as Pérez Nieves and Bonet (2006), Corujo, Fernández-Esquer and Rama (2019), Carratalá and Palau-Sampio (2019).

Table 1. Political groups analysed on Twitter

Political group	Political profile		Type of actor	Number of tweets collected
	Political actor analysed	Political actor analysed		
Esquerra Republicana de Catalunya (ERC)	Pro-independence	ERC	Party	1,567
		Oriol Junquera	Leader	
		Gabriel Rufián (ERC)	Spokesperson	
Junts per Catalunya (JxCAT-JUNTS)	Pro-independence	JxCAT-JUNTS	Party	160
		Carles Puigdemont	Leader	
		Laura Borràs	Spokesperson	
Euzko Alderdi Jeltzalea-Partido Nacionalista Vasco (EAJ-PNV)	Nationalist	EAJ-PNV	Party	2,216
		Andoni Ortuzar	Leader	
		Aitor Esteban	Spokesperson	

	Nationalist	EHBildu	Party	
		Arnaldo Otegui	Leader	
Euskal Herria Bildu (EHBildu)			Spokesperso n	6,233
	Nationalist	Canary Coalition	Party	
			Spokesperso	
		Ana Oramas	n	
		José Miguel Barragán	Spokesperso n	1,561
Coalición Canaria	Constitutionalist	Union of the People of Navarre	Party	
Unión del Pueblo Navarro (UPN)			Leader/Spok espersion	1,079
	Nationalist	Compromís	Party	
		Enric Morera i Català	Leader	
			Spokesperso	
Compromís		Joan Baldoví	n	1,341
	Constitutionalist	PRC	Party	
		Miguel Angel Revilla	Leader	
Partido Regionalista de Cantabria (PRC)			Spokesperso n	1,083
	Nationalist	BNG	Party	
		Xosé Manuel Beiras	Leader	
Bloque Nacionalista Galego (BNG)			Spokesperso n	
Teruel Existe*	Constitutionalist	Teruel Exists	Party	1,723
Total				19,653

Note:* Only the official account of the political party was analysed, because the leader/spokesperson did not have an official Twitter account at the time the data was gathered.

** During the period of data collection the role of spokesperson was assumed by several different politicians in the case of the political party Ciudadanos.

2,730 posts identifying disinformation were collected through two of the main fact-checking journalistic projects in Spain (Maldita.es and Newtral.es) between 16 August 2019 and 15 March 2020 (seven continuous calendar months), through the Relenium package¹ Rvest² packages. The period considered for the identification of this content was longer than the one considered for the Twitter posts, in order to ensure the highest possible number of potential topics associated with disinformation (such as fake news, half-truth, misleading or false content), in the selected fact-checking projects.

The selection of the fact-checking projects (Maldita.es and Newtral.es) was made according to the following criteria:

- These projects are two of the first fact-checking journalism initiatives in Spain. Both were created in 2018. The journalists associated with Newtral.es have been part of the International Fact-Checking Network (IFCN) since 2017.
- These fact-checking projects have been the ones that have generated the most academic interest in Spain by authors such as García and López (2020); Sánchez-Duarte and Magallón (2020) and Bernal-Triviño (2019), because of their analysis of the evolution and viral dissemination of this type of content through social networks. The methodology applied to identify disinformation in both fact-checking projects uses a journalistic approach. In the case of Maldita.es (2020), an active selection is made of content that could be disinformation (according to the level of virality and potential danger) that is then classified as "half-truth", "misleading" or "false". These contents are investigated by a member of their team to determine proof, evidence and associated sources, and the work is validated by the editors in charge of this project. In the case of Newtral.es (2021), every day the team of verifiers collects the statements of key social agents (e.g. politicians and public administration officers), selects the statements with journalistic interest or relevance (in order to assess the transcendence of these statements), verifies the public and official data available through sources and experts, and carries out a

¹ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/Relenium/index.html>

² <https://rvest.tidyverse.org/>

peer verification with this information. The coordinator in charge of the team of verifiers and the editor-in-chief of the project re-verifies these contents, and those that pass the triple verification process are those that are published. This content is then classified as either "fake news" (content that is totally or partially false) and other content without enough evidence to be considered fake news without necessarily being true.

The selection of content to be investigated as possible disinformation by the fact-checking projects considered in this paper is characterised by its highly discretionary nature as a result of the social and linguistic conditioning (Graves, 2016) and political factors (Uscinski, 2015) that influence journalistic work. The results of this study could help fact-checking projects to identify the minority political groups with public representation in Spain with higher levels of co-occurrence around content associated with disinformation. This would make it possible to recognise which of these groups could be favouring the viral dissemination of this type of content within public opinion in Spain, in the terms outlined by Amazeen (2015). These data can also contribute to the identification of the communication strategy employed by these actors when publishing messages or comments with ambiguous language that may or may not contribute to the viral dissemination of this type of content (Lim, 2018). All this information could help fact-checkers in their role as democracy-building tools (Amazeen, 2017).

The totality of messages and misinformation content taken for the development of this work followed the processing procedure shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1.

Procedures for handling messages collected for analysis.

Note: *The library <https://pypi.org/project/polyglot/> was used to detect the language of each tweet collected.

** Through the use of the Stopwords ISO directory (<https://github.com/stopwords-iso>) and the R packages `dplyr` (<https://rsanchezs.gitbooks.io/rprogramming/content/chapter9/dplyr.html>), `Stringi` (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/stringi/index.html>), `Tidyverse` (<https://www.tidyverse.org/>), and `Tidytext` (<https://www.tidytextmining.com/>).

*** Based on the dictionary of terms extracted from <http://cartago.illf.uam.es/grampal/grampal.cgi?m=etiquetario> and <https://github.com/Tvangeste/dsl2mobi/tree/master/wordforms>

^ Using the model <https://pypi.org/project/tmtoolkit/0.6.1/>. The library extracts only names, in lower case, removing special characters, numbers and words shorter than 2 and longer than 20 characters. Each of these elements will be considered as a term or token throughout the analysis.

The level of co-occurrence is made up of five discrete levels, according to the values associated with each of the vectors generated from the Numpy's `qcvt`³ function and the treatment procedure shown in Figure 1. The values are distributed in quintiles that represent the crossings observed at the level of slogans between the messages published by users linked to political groups, and the content identified as disinformation in Maldita.es and Newtral.es. Thus, the levels are established as follows: Very low (between 0 and 20 crossings), Low (between 21 and 38 crossings), Medium (between 39 and 69 crossings), High (between 70 and 108 crossings), and Very high (109 or more crossings). In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the following processes were carried out:

³ <https://numpy.org/>

1. Topic modelling, which help identify the main discursive axes of both the publications of political groups on Twitter and the content identified as misinformation by the fact-checking projects involved. To this end, the methodology used by authors such as Debnath and Bardhan (2020), Song, Kim and Jeong (2014), or Walker, Chandra, Zhang and Van Witteloostuijn (2019) on Topic Modeling (TM) in the study of political narrative contexts, electoral processes in social networks and public policies was applied. TM identifies topics around certain discursive axes based on machine learning techniques and the use of the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) algorithm. These techniques facilitated the automatic analysis process of the 2,730 pieces of content identified as disinformation by the fact-checking projects selected for this work. The LDA model, as pointed out by Mehrotra et al. (2013), focuses on the automatic analysis of content and not on the exact estimation of optimal topics addressed in the content, so metrics aimed at this estimation were used. In our specific case, the metrics proposed by Griffiths and Steyvers (2004), Cao, Xia, Zhang and Tang (2009), Arun, Suresh, Madhavan and Murthy (2010), Mimno et al. (2011) and Deveaud, Sanjaun and Ballot (2014) were taken into consideration to identify the number of topics that maximise or minimise the debate around the contents identified as disinformation by maldita.es and Newtral.es (figure 2).

Figure 2.

Example of metrics used to identify topics in political groups analysed and in content identified as misinformation by Maldita.es and Newtral.es.

Coalición Canaria case

Maldita.es and Newtral.es

Source: Prepared by the authors

2. Statistical analysis of variables associated with the tweets published by the actors linked to the political groups analysed: level of virality, type of messages and level of co-occurrence detected between the tweets and the content identified as misinformation by the fact-checking projects considered by this project.

Results

Regarding specific objective 1 of this study, our Topic Modeling analysis revealed an average number of topics (five on average) that guide the discursive axes developed by these actors on Twitter (table 2).

Table 2. Number of topics

Political group	Political profile	Number of topics
BNG	Nationalist	
Canary Coalition	Nationalist	
Compromís	Nationalist	5
EAJ-PNV	Nationalist	5
EHBildu	Nationalist	

ERC	Pro-independence	5
JxCAT-JUNTS	Pro-independence	
MasPaís	Constitutionalist	5
PRCantabria	Constitutionalist	5
Teruel Exists	Constitutionalist	
UPN	Constitutionalist	

With regard to specific objective 2 and 3, tables and figures 3, 4 and 5 reveal the following results:

Political groups with a constitutionalist profile (UPN, Teruel Existe, Más País and PRC), focused on promoting arguments on Twitter associated with:

- a. The electoral processes experienced during the period under study (April and November 2019) and the negotiation for the formation of the national government.
- b. The confrontation, or search for electoral differences, with other parties at the national or regional level (such as UPN with EHBildu, PSOE and EAJ-PNV, or Más País in the case of Vox and Partido Popular).
- c. Reinforcing the legitimacy of their political projects as valid electoral options for their potential voters in issues of national (CIS, 2020) and regional interest, for instance: healthcare, employment, taxes, budgets, gender violence, socio-political conflicts (such as the judicial decision against those who promoted the unilateral declaration of independence in Catalonia), the depopulation of rural areas of Spain and education (specifically, parents' freedom of choice of educational centres). Each of the political groups here analysed addresses these issues differently: Teruel Existe focuses on rural depopulation and the lack of connection with the rest of Spain; Más País is interested in national issues (employment, national economy and gender violence); UPN is more interested in regional issues (employment, health, the fight against cancer, taxes and the regional budget, and the transfer of powers to the regional government), and national issues (education, freedom of choice of schools, gender violence in other parts of Spain, and the memory of the violence perpetrated by the terrorist group ETA, both in the Basque Country and in the whole country); and PRC is more interested in issues associated with connection/transportation problems and regional business activity.

Table 3. Top 10 topics extracted by LDF in UPN, Teruel Existe, Más País and PRC tweets

		Number of topics	Prob. (β)
Re gio nal poli tica l gro ups wit h a con stit uti ona list poli tica l pro file	UP N	Topic 1	Bildu (0.0676); Navarra (0.0489); Chivite (0.0364); Psn (0.0354); Government (0.0244); Eh (0.0187); Geroa (0.0166); Bai (0.0140); Budgets (0.0135); Socios (0.0130)
		Topic 2	Navarra (0.0852); España (0.0415); Sánchez (0.0223); Upn (0.0218); Nacionalismo (0.0192); Suma (0.0170); Navarrasuma (0.0166); Sumatealamayoría (0.0157); Nacionalistas (0.0144); Vote (0.0140)
		Topic 3	Navarra (0.0496); Government (0.0313); Chivite (0.0154); Health (0.0154); Sum (0.0146); Employment (0.0117); Taxes (0.0100); Millions (0.0096); Euros (0.0088); Tudela (0.0083)
		Topic 4	Navarra (0.0313); Freedom (0.0215); Education (0.0195); Upn (0.0143); Support (0.0143); Day (0.0137); Families (0.0117); Individuals (0.0111); Children (0.0104); Suma (0.0085)
		Topic 5	Chivite (0.0151); Psn (0.0357); Law (0.0321); Government (0.0256); Barkos (0.0246); Euskera (0.0221); Navarra (0.0206); President (0.0206); Politics (0.0186); Decree (0.0151)
		Topic 6	Navarrasuma (0.0202); Eta (0.0202); Work (0.0161); Victims (0.0145); Thank you (0.0137); Tudela (0.0121); Javier (0.0121); Parliament (0.0113); Javierremirez (0.0113); Words (0.0105)
		Topic 1	Teruelexiste (0.0553); Turolenses (0.0407); Provincia (0.0405); Teruel (0.0308); Senado (0.0162); Yatetoca (0.0160); Yatocateruel (0.0141); Voz (0.0125); 10n (0.0120); Movimiento (0.0120)
		Topic 2	Teruel (0.0089); Spain (0.0161); Depopulation (0.0137); Spain (0.0134); Soria (0.0134); Madrid (0.0106); Services (0.0103); Inhabitants (0.0096); Year (0.0093); Population (0.0089)
		Topic 3	Depopulation (0.0474); Spain (0.0471); Teruelexiste (0.0351); Teruel (0.0225); State (0.0181); Country (0.0165); Problem (0.0165); Spain (0.0126); Province (0.0126); Pact (0.0105)

		Yoparopormipueblo (I strike for my people, 0.0750); Espanavaciada (Empty Spain, 0.0603); Paro (0.0303); Pueblos (0.0259); Minutos (0.0251); España (0.0179); Futuro (0.0173); Despoblación (Depopulation, 0.0160); Espanavaciada (Empty Spain, 0.0148);
	Topic 4	Viernes (0.0122)
		Teruel (0.0395); Andorra (0.0160); Tren (0.0140); Zaragoza (0.0120); Provincia (0.0104); Pueblos (0.0084); Transición (0.0084); Años
	Topic 5	(0.0081); Aragón (0.0078); Diariodeteruel (0.0073)
		Teruelexiste (0.0307); Teruel (0.0245); Guitarte (0.0245); Tomás (0.0228); Congreso (0.0199); Diputado (0.0196); Provincia (0.0127);
	Topic 6	Spain (0.0127); Psoe (0.0127); Existe (0.0111)
		Madrid (0.0246); Freedom 0.0146); Pp (0.0132); Violence (0.0125);
	Topic 1	Women (0.0114); Government (0.0088); Years (0.0081); People (0.0079); Life (0.0067); Country (0.0063)
		Country (0.0438); Votadistinto (Vote differently, 0.0365);
		Government (0.0270); Ierrejon (0.0213); Elections (0.0203); People (0.0195); Politics (0.0185); vote/a (0.0180); 10n (0.0170); Blocking
	Topic 2	(0.0157)
		Ierrejon (0.0234); Country (0.0229); Campaign (0.0225); Politics (0.0120); Act (0.0111); Partners (0.0102); Partners (0.0100);
	Topic 3	maspais10n (0.0086); Thank you (0.0083); People (0.0081)
		Country (0.0288); Spain (0.0218); Transition (0.0207); Programme (0.0160); Future (0.0140); Measures (0.0134); Change (0.0128);
Má	Topic 4	Settlement (0.0121); Justice (0.0112); Emergency (0.0095)
s		Ierrejon (0.0431); Government (0.0253); Interview (0.0125); Spain (0.0074); Direct (0.0065); Debate (0.0065); Ciudadanos (0.0065);
Paí	Topic 5	Puedes (0.0065); Manuelacarmena (0.0062); Dialogue (0.0056)
s		Cantabria (0.0490); 10n (0.0419); Cantabriagana (0.0335); Votaprc (0.0236); Congresoes (0.0211); Diputados (0.0211); Prc (0.0160);
	Topic 1	Madrid (0.0145); Josemariamazon (0.0137); Congreso (0.0112)
		Fm (0.0241); Tertulia (0.0236); Horas (0.0190); Cantabria (0.0175);
PR		Dial (0.0164); Diputado (0.0159); Sintoniza (0.0149); josemaria
C	Topic 2	mazon (0.0144); Diputada (0.0134); Prcantabria (0.0128)

	Plenocan (0.0206); Parlacan (0.0188); Cantabria (0.0174); Cantabriaes (0.0127); Diputada (0.0105); Pedro (0.0105); Millones (0.0101);
Topic 3	Hernando (0.0098); Ppcantabria (0.0094); Diputado (0.0090) 10n (0.0347); Cantabriagana (Cantabria wins0.0339); Votaprc (0.0225); Cantabria (0.0156); Buenosdias (0.0156); Tren (0.0122); Prc (0.0092); Santander (0.0084); Mitin (0.0084); Bilbao (0.0080)
Topic 4	Cantabria (0.0529); Day (0.0331); Santander (0.0230); Years (0.0152); Fair (0.0087); Bay (0.0074); Beach (0.0069); Torrelavega (0.0060); Women (0.0060); Year (0.0055)
Topic 5	

Figure 3.

Example of tweets associated with main issues addressed by UPN, Teruel Existe, Más País and PRC.

In the case of political groups with a pro-independence political profile (table 4 and figure 4), the analysis of the topics of the messages collected and analysed allows us to see a communicative context focused on: 1) electoral self-promotion, aimed at promoting electoral activities and arguments oriented towards the legitimacy and worth of their political projects; and 2) confrontation with other political actors at the national level (e.g. Partido Popular, PSOE, Ciudadanos and Vox). Both issues are approached from a discursive axis based on the 'Catalan conflict', which underpins the main argumentative basis of this type of political actors in Spain (the separation of their Autonomous Community from the country). This issue, beyond the existing interest at the autonomous level, is not among the priorities of Spanish society during the period analysed –beyond the month of November 2019, when protests took place in Catalonia because of the decision of the High Court of Justice against those who promoted Catalonia's unilateral declaration of independence with Spain (CIS, 2020). This issue was addressed during the period under analysis by ERC and JxCAT-JUNTS as follows:

- By showing a position of conflict against the judicial decision and trying to associate this decision with anti-democratic measures taken by the national political scene.
- Seeking to generate a context of solidarity with other political groups (EHBildu), by attempting to establish apparently similar comparisons to different events. For example, the judicial measures taken against the leaders of Catalan independence are compared with the decision who

found some people guilty of terrorism for having started a brawl at a bar in Altasu (Basque Country) in 2018.

- Trying to promote the need to activate a negotiating table for independence talks at the level of the Spanish political debate.

Table 4.

Top 10 topics extracted by LDF in ERC and JxCAT-JUNTS

		Number of										
		topics	Prob. (β)									
Autono-	mo-	Topic 1	Years (0,0160); Franco (0,0107); Junqueras (0,0100); People (0,0100); Catalonia (0,0089); Justice (0,0086); Country (0,0086); State (0,0082); Spain (0,0075); Law (0,0071)									
			Topic 2	Gabrielrufian (0.0491); Lafabricarufian (0.0158); Youtube (0.0158); Interview (0.0155); Channel (0.0151); Programme (0.0101); Subscribe (0.0093); Media (0.0089); Week (0.0089); Vox (0.0081)								
				Topic 3	Years (0.0171); Street (0.0148); Fascists (0.0144); Congress (0.0093); Life (0.0089); Day (0.0078); Sir (0.0074); Labour (0.0074); Police (0.0066); Madrid (0.0062)							
					Topic 4	Gabrielrufian (0.0497); Psoe (0.0229); Catalunya (0.0201); Mesa (0.0167); Sánchez (0.0167); Junqueras (0.0152); Pereaaragones (0.0129); Jail (0.0123); Dialogue (0.0116); Conflict (0.0112)						
						Topic 5	Gabrielrufian (0.0336); Rufian (0.0168); Spain (0.0143); Gabriel (0.0115); Psoe (0.0091); Erc (0.0087); People (0.0084); Persons (0.0084); Interview (0.0077); Right (0.0073)					
poli-	tica-	Topic 1	Catalonia (0.0328); Years (0.0287); Justice (0.0287); Freedom (0.0246); Problem (0.0246); Pedro (0.0205); Catalonia (0.0164); Democracy (0.0164); Business (0.0164); Spain (0.0164)									
			Topic 2	Catalunya (0,0476); Sanchezcastejon (0,0346); Barcelona (0,0260); President (0,0173); Rights (0,0130); Year (0,0130); Exile (0,0130); Pabloglesias (0,0130); Prisoners (0,0130); Puigdemont (0,0130)								
				Topic 3	Spain (0.0488); Dialogue (0.0279); People (0.0209); Law (0.0174); Future (0.0174); Chile (0.0140); Council (0.0140); European (0.0140); Hola (0.0140); Laura (0.0140)							
					Topic 4							
						Topic 5						
ind-	epe-	nde-	nce-	poli-	tica-	JxC	I	AT-	pro	JUN	file	TS

	Bar (0.0282); Brawl (0.0211); Psoe (0.0211); Terrorism (0.0211); Eldiarioes (0.0176); Majority (0.0176); Pp (0.0176); President (0.0141); Prosecutor's Office (0.0141); Torra (0.0141)
Topic 4	Stuff (0.0280); Day (0.0240); Judge (0.0240); Government (0.0200); National (0.0200); Police (0.0200); Judgement (0.0200); Supreme (0.0200);
Topic 5	Quimtorraipla (0.0160); Registry (0.0160)
	Years (0.0352); Europe (0.0247); Citizens (0.0211); Jec (0.0211); Economy (0.0176); People (0.0141); Party (0.0141); Persons (0.0141); Prison (0.0141); Thanks (0.0106)
Topic 6	

Figure 4.

Example of tweets associated with the main issues addressed by ERC and JxCAT-JUNTS

As for the groups with a nationalist political profile (Compromis, Coalición Canaria, Compromis, EHBildu, and BNG), table 5 and figure 5 reveal that:

- Groups such as Coalición Canaria and Compromis are the most likely to address issues of national interest such as gender violence and the fight for equal rights for women in society, the state of healthcare and education, regional budgets or the repercussions that Brexit would have on their areas of political action (CIS, 2020), compared to the rest of the groups.
- There is a generalised use of Twitter as a digital space for electoral self-promotion or the search for legitimisation of their political projects. Despite this, Coalición Canaria and Compromis were the least likely to make use of this digital stage for the aforementioned purposes.
- EAJ-PNV, EHBildu, Compromis and BNG are the groups with the most confrontational orientation in Twitter with other regional and national political actors, as well as with public institutions. For example, EHBildu questions the work done by EAJ-PNV with the Zaldívar landfill case; Compromís criticises the PSOE's inability to reach an agreement that avoids a repeat of the April 2019 general elections; EAJ-PNV shows its rejection of the High Court ruling and the government's position on the "Catalan Conflict"; and BNG claims a spot in the Electoral Board and talks about the right of foreigners to vote during the November 2019 general elections. It also shares criticisms against King Felipe II's intervention in his traditional Christmas speech or the refusal of the Spanish State to give information about torturers from the Francoist period.

Table 5.

Top 10 topics extracted by LDF in Coalición Canarias, Compromis, EHBildu, EAJ-PNV and BNG

Re	Number	Prob. (β)
gio	of topics	
nal		Canarias (0.0814); Fuerzacanaria (Canarian strength 0.0475);
poli	Co	Nacionalistas (0.0436); Anioramas (0.0345); Madrid (0.0280);
tica	alic	Votacanarias (0.0238); Congreso (0.0225); 10n (0.0221); Vote
l	ión	Topic 1 (0.0189); Elecciones (0.0182)
gro	Ca	CanaryIslands (0.0416); Government (0.0416); Coalition (0.0180);
ups	nar	Measures (0.0151); Infrastructures (0.0133); Spain (0.0128); Crisis
wit	ias	Topic 2 (0.0123); State (0.0118); Families (0.0114); Trouble (0.0109)

h a nat ion alis t poli tica l pro file	Topic 3	CanaryIslands (0.0543); Government (0.0543); Psoe (0.0205); State (0.0163); Millions (0.0159); Sánchez (0.0130); Data (0.0117); Taxes (0.0117); Months (0.0117); CanaryIslanders (0.0113)
	Topic 4	Tenerife (0.0220); Canary (0.0197); Years (0.0164); Support (0.0158); Work (0.0124); Island (0.0118); Struggle (0.0113); CanaryIslands (0.0102); Year (0.0096); Society (0.0096)
	Topic 5	Coalition (0.0215); Labour (0.0157); Vez (0.0139); Parties (0.0128); Accord (0.0128); Via (0.0116); Psoe (0.0110); Opposition (0.0110); Pensions (0.0099); Cabildo (0.0087)
	Topic 6	Women (0,0217); Fuerzacanaria (Canarian strength, 0,0150); Commitment (0,0132); Island (0,0126); Week (0,0120); Anioramas (0,0108); Lanzarote (0,0102); Team (0,0102); People (0,0102); Fuerteventura (0,0096)
	Topic 7	Canaries (0.0383); Government (0.0243); Anioramas (0.0179); CanaryIslanders (0.0159); Spain (0.0154); Connectivity (0.0149); Morocco (0.0144); Coalition (0.0139); Cook Islands (0.0129); Cook (0.0124)
	Topic 8	Canary Islands (0.0447); Government (0.0172); Labour (0.0149); People (0.0138); Measures (0.0126); Problems (0.0109); Sector (0.0103); Senate (0.0103); Equipoclavijo (0.0092); Commission (0.0086)
	Topic 1	Obloque (0.1005); Anaponton (0.0486); 10n (0.0260); Diputado (0.0227); Entrevista (0.0227); Xunta (0.0227); Bng (0.0195); Candidate (0.0195); Congreso (0.0195); Persons (0.0195)
	Topic 2	Congreso (0.0251); Pp (0.0251); Psoe (0.0209); Vez (0.0209); Democracia (0.0167); Galiza (0.0167); Mesa (0.0167); Vox (0.0167); Cs (0.0126); Cárcel (0.0126)
BN G	Topic 3	Xmbeiras (0.0389); Catalunya (0.0195); Falta (0.0195); Fascismo (0.0195); Nestorrego (0.0195); Noche (0.0195); País (0.0195); Años (0.0156); Español (0.0156); Franco (0.0156)
	Topic 4	Obloque (0.0277); Gobierno (0.0246); Sánchez (0.0246); Psoe (0.0185); Forma (0.0185); Gente (0.0185); Ley (0.0185); Train (0.0185); Vote (0.0185); Pp (0.0154)

		Coup (0.0246); Chile (0.0205); Thanks (0.0205); Millions (0.0205); Regime (0.0205); Bolivia (0.0164); State (0.0164); Piñera (0.0164);
	Topic 5	Spain (0.0123); Europe (0.0123)
		Bng (0.0386); Años (0.0309); Rey (0.0309); Galicia (0.0270); Obloque (0.0193); Diputados (0.0193); Erc (0.0193); Madrid
	Topic 6	(0.0193); Bildu (0.0154); Cup (0.0154)
		Mireiamolla (0.0120); Dana (0.0111); People (0.0108); Change (0.0096); Fight (0.0092); Education (0.0086); Millions (0.0071);
	Topic 1	Emergency (0.0068); Consellera (0.0068); Services (0.0068)
		Pp (0.0223); Government (0.0191); Joanbaldovi (0.0124); Compromis (0.0117); Compromís (0.0113); Years (0.0102); Vox (0.0095);
	Topic 2	Valenciana (0.0088); Spain (0.0088); Life (0.0085)
		10n (0.0244); Políticaútil (0.0215); Méscompromís (0.0212); Política (0.0180); Gobierno (0.0141); Compromis (0.0122); Gente (0.0099);
	Topic 3	Personas (0.0096); Monicaoltra (0.0093); Alacant (0.0090)
		Interview (0.0460); Joanbaldovi (0.0429); Políticaútil (0.0262); Acuerdo (0.0154); Investidura (0.0137); Monicaoltra (0.0134); Gobierno (0.0132); Psoe (0.0130); Sánchez (0.0115); Financiación
	Topic 4	(0.0101)
Co		València (0.0208); Alicante (0.0185); Puerto (0.0147); Ciudad
mp		(0.0112); Compromis (0.0100); Derecha (0.0096); Joanbaldovi
ro		(0.0093); Ampliación (0.0077); Monicaoltra (0.0069);
mis	Topic 5	Emergenciaclimática (0.0069)
		Donostia (0.0127); Day (0.0099); City (0.0097); Employment (0.0091); Vitoriagasteiz (0.0089); Sansebastian (0.0080); Mayor
	Topic 1	0.0067); Future (0.0067); Gipuzkoa (0.0065); Year (0.0063)
		Andoniortuzar (0.049); Eajpvn (0.021); Sentence (0.015); President (0.013); Years (0.011); Herriirratia (0.010); Euskadi (0.010); Case
EA	Topic 2	(0.009); Catalonia (0.009); Dialogue (0.008)
J-		Gobeus (0.0188); Government (0.0178); Basque (0.0142); Navarre
PN		(0.0130); Iurkullu (0.0123); Security (0.0111); Transfers (0.0107);
V	Topic 3	Euskadi (0.0093); Zaldibar (0.0077); Interview (0.0067)

		Aitoresteban (0.0624); Hemeneajpvn (0.0514); 10n (0.0414); Euskadi (0.0257); Andoniortuzar (0.0215); Eajpvn (0.0210); Madrid (0.0160);
	Topic 4	Mikkellegarda (0.0151); Urkullulhk (0.0120); Voxes (0.0100)
		Aitoresteban (0.0301); Andoniortuzar (0.0298); Government (0.0226);
	Topic 5	Psoe (0.0210); Agreement (0.0204); Eajpvn (0.0181); Sánchez (0.0167); Boulevardeitb (0.0146); Euskadi (0.0112); State (0.0111)
		Government (0.0171); State (0.0167); Bildu (0.0161); Eh (0.0151);
	Topic 1	Psoe (0.0135); Mertxeazipurua (0.0121); Arnaldootegi (0.0118); Sánchez (0.0107); Oskarmatute (0.0107); Right (0.0099)
E		Baietz (0.0208); Ehbildu (0.0147); 10n (0.021); Madrid (0.015); Bel
H		(0.014); Pozueta (0.012); Voto (0.011); Congreso (0.008);
B	Topic 2	Ruizdepinedo (0.008)
il		Years (0.0125); State (0.0111); Altsasu (0.0102); Justice (0.0102);
d		Sentence (0.0083); Spain (0.0081); People (0.0066); Catalonia
u	Topic 3	(0.0058); Eta (0.0057)
		Government (0.0098); Ehbildu (0.0073); Pnv (0.0066); People
	Topic 4	(0.0052); Zaldibar (0.0051); Workers (0.0047); Ikerkasanova (0.0045); Gobeus (0.0044); Joninarritu (0.0038); Parliament (0.0038)

Figure 5.

Example of tweets associated with the main issues addressed by Coalición Canarias, Compromis, EHBildu, EAJ-PNV and BNG

Regarding specific objective 4, when we cross-reference the tweets published by the political groups analysed with the content identified as disinformation by Maldita.es and Newtral.es (table 6), we can see that almost half of the tweets published by the parties, leaders and spokespersons of the political groups analysed (4.7 out of every 10 messages) have a medium, high or very high level of co-occurrence with the content detected as disinformation. This allows us to see how, in general terms, the passive or active participation of the groups analysed in disseminating this type of content is high, beyond the fact that this study does not delve into the type of participation assumed by these actors, i.e. whether the co-occurrence is from an active participation (promoting disinformation content from their users) or from a passive participation (by taking issues

addressed by these actors as an argumentative basis for content identified as disinformation disseminated by other users). Table 6 also shows how groups with a pro-independence political profile had a lower than average percentage of co-occurrence than the rest of the nationalist or constitutionalist political groups. Moreover, it can be seen how there are political groups, such as Más País, Coalición Canaria and UPN, whose percentage of co-occurrence is clearly higher than the general average observed in the rest of the groups studied in this study.

Table 6.

Co-occurrence of messages published by the actors analysed and the content identified as disinformation by Maldita.es and Newtral.es

Political group	Level of co-occurrence with content identified as disinformation by Maldita.es and Newtral.es					Cumulative percentage (medium, high, very high co-occurrence)	Difference versus overall average	Level of co-occurrence (mean)
	Very low	Under	Medium	High	Very High			
Canary Coalition	24,28%	22,68%	16,40%	18,45%	18,19%	53,04%	6,19%	
Compromis	33,04%	21,18%	16,70%	18,79%	10,29%	45,78%	-1,07%	
EAJ-PNV	28,47%	23,78%	20,62%	16,97%	10,15%	47,74%	0,89%	
EHBildu	26,82%	25,12%	19,62%	17,74%	10,69%	48,05%	1,20%	
BNG	33,12%	22,08%	20,78%	14,94%	9,09%	44,81%	-2,04%	47,88%
ERC	34,27%	24,19%	19,66%	13,15%	8,74%	41,55%	-5,30%	
JxCAT-JUNTS	36,25%	18,13%	20,00%	20,00%	5,63%	45,63%	-1,22%	43,59%
PRC	35,73%	26,22%	17,45%	10,99%	9,60%	38,04%	-8,81%	
Teruel Exists	30,35%	26,64%	16,08%	16,02%	10,91%	43,01%	-3,84%	
UPN	26,88%	23,35%	15,66%	19,37%	14,74%	49,77%	2,92%	
More Country	25,24%	16,88%	19,91%	18,45%	19,52%	57,88%	11,03%	47,17%
Average percentage of co-occurrence						46,85%		

At a general level, the highest proportion of messages published by the regional political groups analysed with a medium, high or very high level of co-occurrence are retweets (6 out of every 10 posts). The extracted data also allow us to segment the regional political groups analysed into three groups:

- Autonomous political groups, whose level of co-occurrence is concentrated in a higher proportion of retweets (6 or more of every 10 posts are retweets): Coalición Canarias (nationalist), EHBildu (nationalist), JxCAT-JUNTS (pro-independence), ERC (pro-independence) and BNG (nationalist).
- Regional political groups whose level of co-occurrence is close to a balanced distribution between tweets and retweets (5 out of 10 posts): Teruel Existe (constitutionalist), UPN (constitutionalist), Compromís (nationalist) and EAJ-PNV (nationalist).
- Autonomous political groups whose level of co-occurrence is more concentrated at the level of tweets (6 out of 10 publications are original tweets): Más País (constitutionalist) and PRC (constitutionalist).

When analysing the main topics of the content identified as disinformation by the *fact-checking* projects Maldita.es and Newtral.es (table 7) during the collection period we see how these are focused mostly on topics related to: 1) the protests (October, 2019) generated by the judicial decision on pro-independence leaders in Barcelona; 2) electoral content associated with possible pacts between the political groups PSOE and Unidas Podemos; 3) phishing and economic fraud; 4) content published on Twitter and the internet to defraud citizens; 5) Aid received by immigrants in general, especially unaccompanied immigrant minors in Madrid and Spain; 6) Measures promoted by the Spanish government against gender violence; 7) Parental Pin in education; and 8) Risks associated with food consumption.

Table 7.

Top 10 topics extracted by LDF from content identified as disinformation on Maldita.es and Newtral.es, with the highest probability of co-occurrence (β)

Topics	Maldita.es and Newtral.es
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	police (0.02212), video (0.01754), Barcelona (0.01264), sentence (0.01208), Catalonia (0.01178), hoax (0.0102), audio (0.007952), national (0.007901),
Topic 1	networks (0.007647), mossos (0.007494)
	elections (0.01714), Sanchez (0.01472), party (0.01419), Pablo (0.01264), Podemos (0.01211), pedro (0.01211), pp (0.01067), bulo (0.01037), iglesias
Topic 2	(0.0101), psoe (0.01007)
	data (0.02751), message (0.02231), phishing (0.01988), WhatsApp (0.01936), web (0.01873), page (0.01769), company (0.01607), mail (0.01526), sms
Topic 3	(0.01468), post (0.01324)
	bitcoin (0.02547), scam (0.01501), program (0.01111), people (0.01068), money (0.009814), faces (0.008659), investment (0.008371), case (0.008299),
Topic 4	jordi (0.008082), article (0.008082)
	content (0.03095), web (0.01744), tweet (0.01663), publication (0.01545), account (0.0142), capture (0.01395), hoax (0.0137), text (0.009966), headline
Topic 5	(0.009592), evidence (0.008284)
	data (0.01566), year (0.01178), government (0.01145), Spain (0.01035), years (0.0102), Madrid (0.009579), men (0.00819), number (0.008094), community
Topic 6	(0.007089), affirmation (0.00661)
	coronavirus (0.06044), article (0.02041), outbreak (0.01922), china (0.01577), virus (0.01299), video (0.01074), covid19 (0.008152), who (0.007954), health
Topic 7	(0.007887), countries (0.007887)
	video (0.04889), hoax (0.01871), images (0.01845), image (0.01315), photo (0.009758), networks (0.008292), facebook (0.007332), man (0.006927), Spain
Topic 8	(0.006826), him (0.006674)
topic_9	euros (0.0246), Spain (0.02169), aid (0.02022), years (0.01507), immigrants (0.0138), people (0.01192), aid (0.01125), mena (0.009472), Madrid (0.009167), social (0.009014)
topic_10	video (0.01593), education (0.01285), Spain (0.01285), hoax (0.01135), school (0.01097), years (0.0109), children (0.0103), pupils (0.00992), city council (0.009619), parents (0.009018)

The identification of topics associated with the content recognised as disinformation by Maldita.es and Newtral.es allows us, to initially identify the level of high or very high co-occurrence of the tweets published by each political group. If we take into consideration

the discursive centrality shown in figures 3, 4 and 5, this co-occurrence would be centred around the messages related to the electoral processes and political confrontation that took place during the study period, as well as those focused on topics linked to the main socially-recognised problems in Spain, such as gender violence or independence in Catalonia (CIS, 2020). The issues surrounding the election and the Catalan conflict are addressed transversally and from different political perspectives based on a strategy of communicative confrontation with other regional and national political groups. In other cases, such as gender violence, the issue was addressed especially at the level of certain regional political groups with a more constitutionalist and/or nationalist political profile. Finally, regarding specific objective 5, the Chi association test² allows us to confirm the non-existence of a statistically significant dependence ($p=0.357$ and $p=0.543$), between the level of co-occurrence observed of the messages of the political groups analysed with the content collected from Maldita.es and Newtral.es, and the type of tweet published and the level of virality⁴ of the actors linked to the autonomous political groups studied in this study. The only significant statistical relationship observed, based on Chi², is between the level of co-occurrence of the messages analysed with the content identified as disinformation by Maldita.es and Newtral.es and the political profile of the political groups ($p=0.000$). In this relationship, symmetrical association is very low ($V=0.046$) and there is a null directional relationship between the two ($\lambda=0.000$).

Conclusions

This study is based on a probabilistic model applied to Topic Modeling, with its consequent limitations. Therefore, before presenting the main conclusions of this work, we point out the need for further research on this topic using analytical approaches that complement the model used here (e.g. network and qualitative analysis), and that would help obtain a better understanding of the role and intentionality of the political groups analysed.

⁴ The level of virality is an ad-hoc variable that uses a five-level scale (very low - messages with 0 to 27 retweets and likes, low - messages with 28 to 90 retweets and likes, medium - messages with 91 to 262 retweets and likes, high - messages with 263 to 873 retweets and likes, and very high - messages with 874 or more retweets and likes. This variable consists of the sum of likes and retweets distributed in quintiles.

In the promotion of disinformation on social networks in Spain, the data presented in this study allow us to observe a communication strategy by the political groups analysed focused on a certain number of topics that serve to establish relations between them and their potential voters or users interested in the different political projects led by them in Spain, in the terms set out by Piñeiro-Otero and Martínez-Rolan (2021).

The communication strategy applied by the political groups we analysed seems to be based mainly on confrontation among themselves or with other national and/or regional political groups, which marks the approach to the different issues taken as a basis for their visibility and political legitimisation on social networks such as Twitter. This confrontation contributes to the promotion of a scenario of greater political polarisation that conditions public opinion, especially if we take into consideration that the period analysed was conditioned by electoral processes in Spain. This may have contributed to the increase in polarisation, at least in the terms pointed out by authors such as Levi (2019), Scheufele and Krause (2019) and Cañabate (2019). In this context, the issues addressed by each of these groups seem to depend on their political profile when it comes to the issues they choose: problems of national interest or others more focused on electoral self-promotion or autonomous spheres.

The context described so far would be given under a level of co-occurrence of the messages published by these groups and the content identified as disinformation through projects such as Maldita.es and Newtral.es that could be considered high, if we take into account that almost half of the topics addressed in the messages published by these groups are related to the topics associated with these types of content identified as disinformation. This level may also vary according to the political profile of each of the groups studied, based on the inconclusive statistical relationships obtained in this study, which would require more studies to be made. This would help us observe a polarised communicative context that favours the passive or active participation of the groups analysed in the dissemination of disinformation, in the terms set out by authors such as Van der Linden, Maibach, Cook, Leiserowitz and Lewandowsky (2017). Finally, it would allow us to observe a prominent role in the establishment of the "culture of disinformation" indicated by Wardle and Derakshan (2017).

This would not only lead us to accept hypothesis 1 proposed in this paper, and partially accept the proposed hypothesis 2, but would also show a context in which fact-checking projects could benefit from results such as those shown in this paper from the perspective presented by authors such as Lim (2018) or Amazeen (2015, 2017), when identifying and

understanding the potential impact exerted by minority political groups (Uscinski, 2015). Beyond the relative weight of representation that these groups may have in national political institutions, as is the case of the Spanish Congress of Deputies, it is possible that these political groupings are favouring a deterioration in the quality of Spanish public debate (Amazeen, 2015) through their publications on Twitter, in the terms outlined by Lin (2018). Consequently, they would be contributing to the promotion of a social scenario such as the one described by authors already mentioned in this paper (Davidson, *et al.*, 2017, Aguilés & Pecour, 2021; Matamoros-Fernández & Farkas, 2021). This whole situation is taking place under a current political system in Spain that favours polarisation, as Urman (2020) rightly points out, from the "fragmented multiparty system" (Penadés & Pavía, 2016; Ibañez, 2018), which allows for the emergence of a greater number of political actors who exercise their presence in social networks. This contributes to a greater complexity of Spanish political communication, with a spread of polarised, crisis-focused narratives as indicated by authors such as Ferreira (2019) Lupato *et al.* (2020) or Arroyo (2020).

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Figshare at <https://figshare.com/account/home#/projects/114516>.

Disclosure statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

References

- Agarwal, P., Hawkins, O., Amaxopoulou, M., Dempsey, N., Sastry, N. & Wood, E. (2021). Hate speech in political discourse: A case study of UK MPs on Twitter. Proceedings of the 32nd ACM Conference on Hypertext and Social Media. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3465336.3475113>
- Aguilés, A. V., & Pecourt, J. (2021). Antifeminismo y troleo de género en *Twitter*. Estudio de la subcultura trol a través de # STOPfeminazis. *Teknokultura*, 18(1), 33-44.
- Alonso-Muñoz, L., & Casero-Ripollés, A. (2021). ¿Buscando al culpable? La estrategia discursiva en *Twitter* de los actores políticos populistas europeos en tiempos de crisis. *Cultura, Lenguaje y Representación*, 26, 29-45. DOI <https://doi.org/10.6035/clr.5827>
- Amezeen, M. (2017) Journalistic interventions: The structural factors affecting the global emergence of fact-checking. *Journalism*. v. 21, n. 1, p. 95-111.
- Amazeen. *Critical Review: A Journal of Politics and Society*. v. 27, n. 2, p. 1-10. 2015.
- Ardia, D., Ringel, E., Ekstrand, V. S., & Fox, A. (2020). *Addressing the decline of local news, rise of platforms, and spread of mis-and disinformation online*. University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill.
- Arun, R.; Suresh, V.; Veni, C.E.; Narasimha, M.N. (2010) On Finding the Natural Number of Topics with Latent Dirichlet Allocation: Some Observations. *Neurocomputing: An International Journal*. v. 72, n. 7-9, p. 1775–1781.
- Baumann Z. (2015). *Modernidad Líquida*. Madrid: Fondo de Cultura Económica.
- Benkler, Y., Roberts, H., and Zuckerman, E. (2017). Study: Breitbart-Led Right-Wing Media Ecosystem Altered Broader Media Agenda. *Columbia Journalism Review*, March 3. <http://www.cjr.org/analysis/breitbart-media-trump-harvard-study.php>.
- Bernal-Triviño, A.; Clares-Gavilán, J. (2019) Uso del móvil y las redes sociales como canales de verificación de fake news. El caso de Maldita.es. *El Profesional de la Información*. v. 28, n. 3.
- Bradshaw, S., & Howard, P. (2017). Troops, Trolls and Troublemakers: A Global Inventory of Organized Social Media Manipulation. In *Computational Propaganda Research Project* (pp. 1–37). Oxford Internet Institute.
- Cañabate, J. P. (2019). Unfaking News. Cómo combatir la desinformación. *Estudios sobre el Mensaje Periodístico*, 25(2), 1267-1269.

- Cao, J., Xia, T.; Li, J.; Zhang, Y.; Tang, S. (2009) A density-based method for adaptive LDA model selection. *Neurocomputing: An International Journal*. v. 72, n. 7-9, p. 1775–1781.
- Carratalá, A., & Palau-Sampio, D. (2019). Entre el activismo y la mediatización: encuadres de partidos y prensa en la campaña catalana de 2017. *Revista de comunicación*, 18(2), 73-91.
- CIS (2020). Tres problemas principales que existen actualmente en España. http://www.cis.es/cis/export/sites/default/Archivos/Indicadores/documentos_html/TresProblemas.html
- Cinelli, M.; De Francisci, G.; Galeazzi, A.; Quattrocioni, W.; Starnini, M. (2020). The echo chamber effect on social media. *PNSA*. v. 111, n. 9, e2023301118.
- Correia, J.C., Amaral, I. (2021). A deriva da desinformação: uma ameaça à identidade jornalística. En *De qué hablamos cuando dizemos journalismo*. Covilha: Universidad de Beira Interior.
- Correia, J.C., Jerónimo, P. & Gradim, A. (2019). Fake news: emotion, belief and reason in selective sharing in contexts of proximity, *Brazilian Journalism Research*, v. 15, n. 3, 590-613.
- Corujo, A., Fernández-Esquer, C., & Rama, J. (2019). ¿Quién vota a los partidos nacionalistas en España? Un análisis de las bases electorales de Coalición Canaria. *Revista Española de Ciencia Política*.
- Davidson, T., Warmesley, D., Macy, M., & Weber, I. (2017, May). Automated hate speech detection and the problem of offensive language. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media* (Vol. 11, No. 1, pp. 512-515).
- Debnath, R.; Bardhan, R. (2020) India nudges to contain COVID-19 pandemic: A reactive public policy analysis using machine-learning based topic modelling. *PLoS ONE*. v. 15, n. 9, e0238972.
- Deveaud, R.; Sanjuan, E.M.; Ballot, P. (2014). Accurate and Effective Latent Concept Modeling for Ad Hoc Information Retrieval. *Document Numérique*, p. 61–84.
- Estrada-Cuzcano, A., Alfaro-Mendives, K. y Saavedra-Vásquez, V. (2020). Desinformación, posverdad y noticias falsas: precisiones conceptuales, diferencias, similitudes y yuxtaposiciones. *Información, Cultura y Sociedad*, 42, 93-106.

- Farkas, J., Schou, J., y Neumayer, Ch. (2018). Platformed antagonism: racist discourses on fake Muslim Facebook pages. *Critical Discourse Studies*, 15(5), 463-480. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17405904.2018.1450276>
- Fernández Esquer, C. (2016). Desproporcionalidad y gobernabilidad. *Agenda Pública*, 29-3-2016. Disponible en: <http://agendapublica.es/desproporcionalidad-y-gobernabilidad/>
- Ferreira, C. (2019). Vox como representante de la derecha radical en España: un estudio sobre su ideología. *Revista Española de Ciencia Política*, 51, 73-98. <https://recyt.fecyt.es/index.php/recp/article/view/72190>
- Frame, A. y Brachotte, G. (2015). Le tweet stratégique: Use of Twitter as a PR tool by French politicians, en *Public Relations Review*, 41(2), 278-287.
- Galvañ, A. N., & Giménez, C. O. (2020). Discurso del odio en radio: análisis de los editoriales de las cadenas COPE y SER tras la llegada del Aquarius a España. *Miguel Hernández Communication Journal*, (11), 117-138
- García-Orosa, B. y López-García, X. (2019). Language in social networks as a communication strategy: Public administration, political parties and civil society. *Communication & Society. Vol 32 No 1 (2019). Special Issue: Credibility and Trust in Post-Truth Times and the Network Society*. <https://doi.org/10.15581/003.32.1.107-125>
- García, G.; López, X. (2021) La verificación de datos en Europa. Análisis de 5 iniciativas europeas: Maldita.es, Newtral, Pagella Política, Les Décodeurs y BBC Reality Check. *adComunica: Revista científica de estrategias, tendencias e innovación en comunicación*. n. 21, p. 235-264.
- Graves, L. (2016) Anatomy of a Fact Check: Objective Practice and the Contested Epistemology of Fact Checking. *Communication, Culture & Critique*. V. 10, n. 3, p. 518-537.
- Griffiths, T.; Steyvers, M. (2004). Finding scientific topics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 101 Suppl 1(Suppl 1), 5228–5235. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0307752101>
- Guarino, S., Trino, N., Celestini, A., Chessa, A., & Riotta, G. (2020). Characterizing networks of propaganda on twitter: a case study. *Applied Network Science*, 5(1), 1-22.

- Hrčková, A.; Srba, I.; Móro, R.; Blaho, R.; Šimko, J.; Návrat, P.; Bielíková, M. (2019). Unravelling the basic concepts and intents of misbehavior in post-truth society. *Bibliotecas. Anales de Investigación*. v. 15, n. 3, p. 421-428.
- Ibañez, P. (2018). *La patria es la gente. Análisis del discurso nacional-popular de Unidas Podemos en Twitter*. [Trabajo Fin de Máster]. Universitat Jaume I.
- Lamerichs, N, Dennis, M. C, Puerta, R. R, and Lange-Bohmer. A (2018). Elite Male Bodies: The Circulation of Alt-Right Memes and the Framing of Politicians on Social Media. *Participations* 15 (1): 180–206.
- Lim, C. (2018) Checking how fact-checkers check. *Research & Politics*. v. 5, n. 3, p. 1-7..
- Levi, S. (2019), *#Fakeyou. Fake news y desinformación*. Rayo Verde Editorial.
- Lupato, F., Ruíz, L. Sánchez, G. (2020). La derecha española dividida: posiciones ideológicas y clivaje territorial. *Política y Sociedad*, 57(3), 719-745. <https://doi.org/10.5209/poso.69207>
- MALDITA.ES. *Metodología de Maldito Bulo*. Disponible en: <https://maldita.es/metodologia-de-maldito-bulo>. Accedido en: 19 de diciembre de 2021.
- Marwick, A., & Lewis, R. (2017). Media manipulation and disinformation online. *New York: Data & Society Research Institute*, 7-19.
- Matamoros-Fernández, A., & Farkas, J. (2021). Racism, hate speech, and social media: A systematic review and critique. *Television & New Media*, 22(2), 205-224.
- Mehrotra, R.; Sanner, S.; Buntine, W.; Xie, L. (2013) Improving LDA topic models for microblogs via tweet poolings and automatic labeling. *Proceedings of the 36th international ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval* (889-892). Association for Computing Machinery (ACM). Disponible en: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2484028.2484166>.
- Mimno, D.; Wallach, H.; Talley, E.; Leenders, M.; Mccallum, A. (2011). *Optimizing Semantic Coherence in Topic Models*, 2011. Disponible en: <http://dirichlet.net/pdf/mimno1loptimizing.pdf>. Accedido en: 21 de junio de 2021.
- Newman, N., Fletcher, R., Shulz, A., Andi, S., Roberston, C. & Nielsen, R. (2021). *Reuters institute digital news report 2021 (Vol. 2021)*. Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism.

- NEWTRAL.ES. *Metodología y transparencia*. Disponible en: <<https://www.newtral.es/metodologia-transparencia/>>. Accedido en: 19 de diciembre de 2021.
- Olmo y Romero, J.A. (2019). Desinformación: concepto y perspectivas. En *Revista CiberElcano*. N. 43. Madrid: Real Instituto Elcano. Recuperado de <http://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/wps/wcm/connect/3ac69a0d-5b29-4b12-8cf3-af3c5ff3b2cb/ARI41-2019-OlmoRomero-Desinformacion-concepto-y-perspectivas.pdf?MOD=AJPERES&CACHEID=3ac69a0d-5b29-4b12-8cf3-af3c5ff3b2cb>
- Penadés, A. y Pavía Miralles, J. M. (2016). *La reforma electoral perfecta*. Madrid: Los Libros de la Catarata.
- Pérez-Nievas, S., & Bonet, E. (2006). Identidades regionales y reivindicación de autogobierno. El etnorregionalismo en el voto a partidos nacionalistas de Bélgica, España y Reino Unido. *Revista Española de Ciencia Política*, 15, 123-161.
- Piazza, J. (2020). Politician hate speech and domestic terrorism. *International Interactions*, 46(3), 431-453. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03050629.2020.1739033>
- Piñeiro-Otero, Teresa; Martínez-Rolan, Xabier (2021). Step outside and say that: analysis of hate speech against women on Twitter. *PROFESIONAL DE LA INFORMACION*, 30(5). <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2021.sep.02>
- Said-Hung, E.; Merino-Arribas, M.; Martínez-Torres, J. (2021). Evolución del debate académico en la Web of Science y Scopus sobre unfaking news (2014-2019). *Estudios sobre el mensaje periodístico*. v. 26, n. 3, p. 961-971.
- Sánchez, Ó. (2017). El fin (momentáneo) del bipartidismo en España: análisis de los resultados electorales de 2015 y 2016. *Revista Española de Derecho Constitucional*, 109, 237-260. doi: <https://doi.org/10.18042/cepc/redc.109.09>
- Sánchez-Duarte, J.; Magallón, R. (2020) Infodemia y COVID-19. Evolución y viralización de informaciones falsas en España. *Revista española de comunicación en salud*. n. 1, p. 31-41.
- Scheufele, D. y Krause, N. (2019). Science audiences, misinformation, and fake news. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(16), 7662-7669.
- Song, M., Kim, M. y Jeong, Y. K. (2014). Analyzing the political landscape of 2012 Korean presidential election in Twitter. *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, 29(2), 18-26.

- Søe, S. (2018), "Algorithmic detection of misinformation and disinformation: Gricean perspectives", *Journal of Documentation*, 74 (2), pp. 309-332.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-05-2017-0075>
- Urman, A. (2020). Context matters: political polarization on Twitter from a comparative perspective. *Media, culture & society*, 42(6), 857-879.
- Uscinski, J. (2015) The Epistemology of Fact Checking (is Still Naïve): Rejoinder to Amazeen. *Critical Review: A Journal of Politics and Society*. v. 27, n. 2, p. 1-10.
- Van der Linden, S., Maibach, E., Cook, J., Leiserowitz, A. y Lewandowsky, S. (2017), Inoculating Against Misinformation, *Science*, 358 (6367), pp. 1141–1142.
<https://doi.org/10.117863/CAM.26207>
- Walker, R., Chandra, Y., Zhang, J., van Witteloostuijn, A. (2019). Topic Modeling the Research-Practice Gap in Public Administration. *Public Administration Review*, 79(6), 931-937.
- Wardle, C. y Derakshan, H. (2017). *Information Disorder: Toward an interdisciplinary framework for research and policy making*. Council of Europe.
<https://rm.coe.int/%20information-disorder-toward-an-interdisciplinary-framework-for-researc/168076277c>